

1 Model-free adaptive fault-tolerant control 2 for the floating offshore wind turbine with 3 multiple blade root moment sensor faults

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6

7 Abstract

8 Floating offshore wind turbines (FOWTs) have developed rapidly because they
9 are suitable for deep sea and have high power generation efficiency. However, the
10 control of FOWTs is also very tricky. The main challenges include the difficulty of
11 accurate modeling of FOWTs and the higher failure rate of components. Therefore,
12 this paper proposes a model-free adaptive fault-tolerant control scheme for blade root
13 moment sensor faults. Through model-free adaptive control strategy, an individual
14 pitch controller and a fault compensator are designed to avoid the mathematical
15 modeling of FOWT. The proposed fault-tolerant control scheme does not need any
16 fault diagnosis and isolation, and transforms the fault dynamic compensation process
17 into a real-time control problem for nonlinear systems. The proposed control strategy
18 is simulated and tested by FAST, and the results show that the proposed strategy can
19 not only keep the bearing load of the wheel balanced, but also reduce the movement
20 of the floating platform and significantly reduce the bearing load of the FOWT. In
21 addition, the output power is closer to the rated power, which verifies the excellent
22 fault tolerance capability of the strategy under multiple blade root moment sensor
23 failures.

24

25 **Keyword:** floating offshore wind turbines; individual pitch control; fault-tolerant
26 control; model-free adaptive control; blade root moment sensor failure

27 1. Introduction

28 Wind energy has gradually become the mainstream energy production form to
29 meet the future social needs (Pöschke et al., 2022). Compared with onshore wind
30 power generation, offshore wind power generation can obtain more abundant wind

31 energy resources and higher power conversion efficiency, and has the advantages of
32 green environmental protection. Therefore, the technology of offshore wind power
33 generation has entered a rapid development stage (He et al., 2020). Compared with
34 offshore fixed pile wind turbines, the advantages of floating offshore wind turbines
35 (FOWTs) are obvious in terms of economy, ease of installation and large capacity,
36 especially in deep water (Campanile et al., 2018). However, FOWT is subject to
37 higher structural and fatigue loads due to the greater compliance of large structures
38 and highly asymmetric wind loads. This increased load can lead to rapid wear or
39 damage of structural components, reduced service life, and increased maintenance
40 costs (Qiao et al., 2015).

41 The traditional variable speed rotor and collective pitch control (CPC)
42 technology have limited control over the fatigue load of wind turbines due to rotor
43 yaw error, shaft tilt, wind shear and turbulence (Badihi et al., 2021). Therefore,
44 individual pitch control (IPC) technology is used to cope with highly complex
45 operational loads in FOWTs without affecting the power generation (Zhang et al.,
46 2021). Namik et al. (2008) used IPC strategy to design a state feedback controller
47 (SFC) by formulating the dynamics of barge type FOWT in the form of state space, in
48 order to explore the feasibility of applying IPC based SFC to optimize system
49 operation. Chaaban et al. (2013, 2014) used the model predictive control (MPC)
50 method to design an individual pitch controller to solve the problem of equivalent
51 fatigue load of blades and platform behavior when manipulating rotor speed. Yang et
52 al. (2014) proposed a new IPC method, which combines wind suppression disturbance
53 regulation controller (DAC) and MPC to predict and compensate the impact of wind
54 wave disturbance. Sarkar et al. (2020) adopted a new IPC technology based on
55 wavelet LQR (W-LQR) to solve the conflict between speed and torque control
56 requirements of spar-type FOWT for the first time. Gutierrez et al. (2022) proposed an
57 adaptive second-order sliding mode control algorithm based on the super-torsion
58 control law, which has a very small number of adjustment parameters and low
59 computational requirements.

60 The IPC methods reported in the above studies assumes that all components are
61 in satisfactory operating conditions and all states are measurable. However, the harsh
62 offshore meteorological conditions and the design of the floating structure make the
63 sensors and actuators in FOWT operation susceptible to failures (Li et al., 2022). In
64 order to allow FOWTs to maintain system performance in case of failure,
65 fault-tolerant control techniques (Kamarzarrin et al., 2022; Jain et al., 2020) are
66 applied to individual pitch control, which is called fault-tolerant individual pitch
67 control (FTIPC), and only a few studies have been published. Bachinski et al. (2013)
68 first applied FTC to spar-type FOWT with the pitch actuator failed. Cho et al. (2018)
69 proposed a FTIPC method based on Kalman filter and threshold H_2/H_∞ technology
70 to deal with the fault of pitch angle sensor and actuator of spar-type FOWT. Liu et al.
71 (2020) combined model-based fault diagnosis method with subspace predictive
72 repetitive control, and proposed a new fast adaptive FTIPC method to solve the stuck
73 fault of pitch actuator.

74 Whether for pitch angle sensor failure or pitch actuator failure, the above studies

75 rely on the model information of the controlled system and require fault diagnosis,
76 fault isolation, or parameter estimation to construct fault-tolerant control strategies.
77 For the FOWT with full coupling of aero-hydro-servo-elastic dynamics under the
78 combined action of wind, wave and current, modeling/estimation errors or unmodeled
79 dynamics are inevitable, so there are still deficiencies in the application of the above
80 fault-tolerant schemes to FOWTs. In addition, although the pitch sensors and
81 actuators considered in the above studies are critical to the realization of the IPC
82 scheme, the failures of blade root moment sensors may be ignored. The performance
83 improvement of the blade root moment sensor is a challenge in the IPC system, which
84 plays a key role in reducing the uneven blade load of large wind turbines, especially
85 for the offshore wind turbines (OWTs) operating in harsh environments such as
86 lightning, salt spray, humidity and corrosion. OWT has a higher failure rate of blade
87 load sensors with an average of one failure per year. For OWTs with three blades, the
88 failure rate is approxi-mately three failures per year (Wei et al., 2008). Stotsky et al.
89 (2014) proposed a blade root moment sensor fault detection method that relies on the
90 blade load model and light detection and ranging (LIDAR). Wei et al. (2008)
91 investigated the problem of blade root moment sensor fault detection based on the
92 Kalman filter. However, the design of fault-tolerant control methods is not included in
93 any of the above studies.

94 Motivated by above problems, this paper proposes a model-free adaptive
95 fault-tolerant IPC scheme for blade root moment sensor faults without any prior
96 modeling of FOWTs. As an adaptive fault-tolerant control strategy, the proposed
97 scheme is different from the traditional passive fault-tolerant control that only aims at
98 specific types of faults and the active fault-tolerant control strategy relies on fault
99 diagnosis and isolation, does not need any fault detection and diagnosis, and
100 dynamically recovers multiple blade root moment sensor faults through the adaptive
101 compensator. Specifically, the contributions of this paper are as follows.

102 (1) An individual pitch controller is designed based on model-free adaptive
103 control method, which does not rely on the model information of FOWTs and
104 effectively avoids the adverse effects caused by modeling errors and unmodeled
105 dynamics.

106 (2) A blade root moment sensor fault compensator is developed, which does not
107 need any fault diagnosis and isolation. The dynamic fault compensation process is
108 transformed into a nonlinear system real-time control problem.

109 (3) The model-free adaptive fault-tolerant individual pitch control scheme
110 consisting of the above controller and fault compensator is extensively tested in FAST,
111 which verified its effectiveness and robustness under the fixed deviation fault, drift
112 deviation fault, complete failure and coexistence of multiple faults of blade root
113 moment sensor.

114 The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews the FOWT
115 benchmark and the types blade root moment sensor failure. In Section 3, a model-free
116 adaptive fault-tolerant individual pitch control scheme for FOWT is proposed. The
117 simulation results are presented and discussed in Section 4. Section 5 concludes the
118 paper.

119 **2. Benchmark model of FOWT and blade root moment**
 120 **sensor failures**

121 **2.1 The benchmark model of FOWT**

122 The numerical model adopted in this paper is the OC4-Deepcwind
 123 semi-submersible floating wind turbine developed by the University of Maine
 124 (Coulling et al., 2013), as shown in Figure 1. The wind turbine model is the famous
 125 NREL 5 MW wind turbine. The parameters of the wind turbine and the
 126 semi-submersible floating platform are shown in Table 1 and Table 2. The nonlinear
 127 model of the FOWT with all the above parts combined has 22 degrees of freedom
 128 (DOF). The details of dynamic modeling of the 22-DOF system are not shown in this
 129 paper, and the detailed modeling details can be found in Jonkman (2007).

130
 131 Figure 1 The structure of OC4-Deepcwind semi-submersible floating wind turbine
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133 Table 1 Parameters of 5MW offshore floating wind turbine of NREL

Attribute	Value
Cut-in Speed $/(m \cdot s^{-1})$	3
Rated Speed $/(m \cdot s^{-1})$	11.4
Cut-out Speed $/(m \cdot s^{-1})$	25
Rotor Diameter/m	63
Rated Power/MW	5
Rated Rotor Speed $/(r \cdot min^{-1})$	12.1

Rated generator Speed/(r · min ⁻¹)	1.1737×10 ³
Transmission Ratio	97:1

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135 Table 2 Parameters of the semi-submersible floating platform

Attribute	Value
Draft/m	20
Elevation of platform top above SWL/m	10
Depth to top of base columns below SWL/m	14
Platform mass/kg	13444000
Displacement/m ³	13986
Center of mass below SWL/m	14.4
Platform roll inertia/(kg · m ²)	8.011 × 10 ⁹
Platform pitch inertia/(kg · m ²)	8.011 × 10 ⁹
Platform yaw inertia/(kg · m ²)	1.391 × 10 ⁹

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137 2.2 Blade root moment sensor failures

138 For FOWTs with individual pitch control systems, the failure of the blade root
 139 moment sensor can lead to unreasonable blade pitch angles, unbalancing the wheel
 140 rotation and potentially resulting in poor performance or damage to the wind turbine,
 141 so proper functioning of the blade root moment sensor is critical for successful
 142 individual pitch control applications. As shown in Figure 2, blade root moment sensor
 143 failures include four categories: decreased accuracy, fixed bias, drift bias, and
 144 complete failure (Yang et al., 2022). Among them, fixed bias and drift bias failures are
 145 not easy to detect and can cause a series of unpredictable problems, making the
 146 system not work properly for a long time. Therefore, in this paper, we mainly consider
 147 fixed bias, drift bias faults and complete failure, and all three types of faults can be
 148 equated to the following functions, when taking $a_c(k)$ a suitable dynamic value.

$$149 M_m(k) = a_c(k) \cdot M_a(k) \quad (1)$$

150 Where $M_m(k)$ is the measured blade root moment, $M_a(k)$ is the true blade root
 151 moment, and $a_c(k)$ is the dynamic equivalent fault factor, and the sensor is fault-free
 152 when $a_c(k)=1$.

153

154

Figure 2 The types of blade root moment sensor failure

155 3. Design of model-free adaptive fault-tolerant control 156 strategy

157 As described in Section 2.1, although the mathematical model of the FOWT can
158 be obtained by using the dynamics theory, the model verification is very difficult. In
159 addition, it is rather difficult to obtain a control model to represent the operating state
160 of the FOWT under random meteorological conditions. Thus, the individual pitch
161 controller (IPC) and fault adaptive compensator are designed using MFAC without
162 any modeling of the FOWT in this section, to achieve adaptive fault-tolerant pitch
163 control of FOWTs under the blade root moment sensor faults described in Section 2.2.

164 3.1 Individual pitch control

165 IPC is usually realized by feedback of blade root bending moment. Specifically,
166 the blade root bending moment in the rotating coordinate system is converted into the
167 tilt and yaw components in the fixed coordinate system by Coleman transformation,
168 as shown in (2). The tilt and yaw control quantities are obtained by designing a
169 reasonable controller.

170 The pitch system after Coleman transform can be represented as a discrete
171 system as follows (3).

$$172172 \quad \begin{bmatrix} M_{\text{tilt}} \\ M_{\text{yaw}} \end{bmatrix} \frac{2}{3} \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta) & \cos(\theta + \frac{2}{3}\pi) & \cos(\theta + \frac{4}{3}\pi) \\ \sin(\theta) & \sin(\theta + \frac{2}{3}\pi) & \sin(\theta + \frac{4}{3}\pi) \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} M_{m,1} \\ M_{m,2} \\ M_{m,3} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

$$173 \quad M_{t\&y}(k+1) = f(M_{t\&y}(k), \dots, M_{t\&y}((k - n_{p1}), u_{t\&y}(k), \dots, u_{t\&y}(k - n_{q1})) \quad (3)$$

174 where $f(\cdot)$ is the unknown nonlinear function, n_{p1} and n_{q1} are the coefficients.

175 $M_{t\&y}(k) = [M_{\text{tilt}}(k) \ M_{\text{yaw}}(k)]^T$ and $u_{t\&y}(k) = [u_{\text{tilt}}(k) \ u_{\text{yaw}}(k)]^T$ denotes the
176 output and input.

177 According to the MFAC (Wang et al., 2020; Li et al., 2021), the system (3) can
178 be expressed as (4). Under the conditions that the system is controllable and
179 observable, the partial derivative of the control input signal exists, and the system is
180 continuous and satisfies the generalized Lipschitz assumption, considering the control
181 input criterion function expressed in (6) and the estimation criterion function of the
182 pseudo derivative expressed in (7), the IPC based on the compact format linearization
183 method expressed in (8)-(10) can be given.

$$184 \quad \Delta M_{t\&y}(k+1) = \Phi_1(k) \cdot \Delta u_{t\&y}(k) \quad (4)$$

$$185 \quad \Phi_1(k) = \begin{bmatrix} \phi_{11}(k) & \phi_{12}(k) \\ \phi_{21}(k) & \phi_{22}(k) \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

$$186 \quad J(u_{t\&y}(k)) = \|M_{t\&y}^*(k+1) - M_{t\&y}(k+1)\|^2 + \lambda \|u_{t\&y}(k) - u_{t\&y}(k-1)\|^2 \quad (6)$$

$$187 \quad J(\Phi_1(k)) = \|M_{t\&y}(k) - M_{t\&y}(k-1) - \Phi_1(k) \cdot \Delta u_{t\&y}(k-1)\|^2 + \mu_1 \|\Phi_1(k) - \hat{\Phi}_1(k-1)\|^2 \quad (7)$$

$$188 \quad \hat{\Phi}_1(k) = \hat{\Phi}_1(k-1) + \frac{\eta_1 \Delta u_{t\&y}(k-1)}{\mu_1 + \|\Delta u_{t\&y}(k-1)\|^2} \cdot (\Delta M_{t\&y}(k) - \hat{\Phi}_1(k-1) \Delta u_{t\&y}(k-1)) \quad (8)$$

$$190 \quad \hat{\Phi}(k) = \hat{\Phi}(1), \text{ if } |\hat{\Phi}(k)| < \varepsilon, \text{ or } |\Delta u_{t\&y}(k-1)| < \varepsilon \quad (9)$$

$$191 \quad u_{t\&y}(k) = u_{t\&y}(k-1) + \frac{\rho_1 \hat{\Phi}(k)}{\lambda_1 + \|\hat{\Phi}(k)\|^2} (M_{t\&y}^*(k+1) - M_{t\&y}(k)) \quad (10)$$

192 where λ_1 is a positive weighting factor, $M_{t\&y}^*(k+1)$ is the reference output at $k+1$, μ_1 is a positive weighting factor, and $\hat{\Phi}(k-1)$ is an estimate of the pseudo derivative at $k-1$; η_1 and ρ_1 denote the sequence of steps, respectively, and ε is a sufficiently small positive number.

196 The IPC components $\Delta\beta = [\Delta\beta_1 \ \Delta\beta_2 \ \Delta\beta_3]^T$ of the three blades obtained through
197 inverse Coleman transformation from $u_{t\&y}(k)$ obtained from the above IPC.

$$198198 \quad \begin{bmatrix} \Delta\beta_1 \\ \Delta\beta_2 \\ \Delta\beta_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta) & \sin(\theta) \\ \cos(\theta + \frac{2}{3}\pi) & \sin(\theta + \frac{2}{3}\pi) \\ \cos(\theta + \frac{4}{3}\pi) & \sin(\theta + \frac{4}{3}\pi) \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} u_{\text{tilt}}(k) \\ u_{\text{yaw}}(k) \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

199 3.2 Blade root moment fault adaptive compensator

200 From (1), it can be seen that all types of sensor faults can be described by the
201 equivalent fault factor a_c . Similarly, all sensor faults can be offset by the equivalent
202 compensation factor r_{a_c} to the effect of the equivalent fault factor a_c . Theoretically,
203 r_{a_c} and a_c should be reciprocal, so the focus of this section is to design an adaptive
204 compensator to dynamically solve for the equivalent compensation factor r_{a_c} to
205 compensate for the blade root moment sensors dynamically in real-time.

206 As shown in Figure 3(a), when there is no fault in the blade root moment sensor,
207 the three blade root moment varies periodically, they are basically the same except for
208 the phase difference of $2\pi/3$. When the blade root moment sensor failure occurs, the
209 inaccurate moment value is fed back to the individual pitch controller to derive an
210 unreasonable pitch angle command, resulting in an imbalance of the load on the three
211 blades, and this imbalance of the root waving load in the rotating coordinate system

212212 can be more intuitively demonstrated by $\Delta M_m = [\Delta M_{m,1}, \Delta M_{m,2}, \Delta M_{m,3}]^T$ obtained by
213 the Coleman transform and its inverse conversion as expressed in (12). Figure 3 (b)
214 shows the balanced performance of ΔM_m under the condition of fault-free. When
215 sensor 1 has a slight fault of $a_{c,1}=0.8$, as shown in Figure 3 (c) and 3 (d), the output

216 value of blade 1 root flapping moment in Figure 3 (c) is smaller than that of blades 2
 217 and 3, and the three blades' flapping moment M_m is slightly unbalanced. From Figure
 218 3 (d), it can be seen that $\Delta M_{m,1}$ is obviously smaller than the other two, and the
 219 sensor 1 fault will also affect the blade root load of blades 2 and 3, and ΔM_m has an
 220 obvious imbalance. The degree of this imbalance can be quantified by the mean value
 221 of ΔM_m . Taking the 18m/s average turbulent wind as an example, the mean value of
 222 ΔM_m under different faults of sensor 1 is shown in Table 3.

$$223223 \quad \begin{bmatrix} \Delta M_{m,1} \\ \Delta M_{m,2} \\ \Delta M_{m,3} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta) & \sin(\theta) \\ \cos(\theta + \frac{2}{3}\pi) & \sin(\theta + \frac{2}{3}\pi) \\ \cos(\theta + \frac{4}{3}\pi) & \sin(\theta + \frac{4}{3}\pi) \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta) & \cos(\theta + \frac{2}{3}\pi) & \cos(\theta + \frac{4}{3}\pi) \\ \sin(\theta) & \sin(\theta + \frac{2}{3}\pi) & \sin(\theta + \frac{4}{3}\pi) \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} M_{m,1} \\ M_{m,2} \\ M_{m,3} \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

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225 Figure 3 Blade root moment M_m and transformed moment ΔM_m under fault-free and fault
 226 scenarios

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Table 3 The mean value of ΔM_m under different fault scenarios of sensor 1

Fault scenario	Equivalent fault factor	Ideal equivalent compensation factor	$\Delta M_{m,1}$	$\Delta M_{m,2}$	$\Delta M_{m,3}$
$a_{c,1} < 0$	$a_{c,1}=0.50$	$r_{a_{c,1}}=2.00$	-1518.43	635.60	882.83
	$a_{c,1}=0.70$	$r_{a_{c,1}}=1.43$	-843.43	346.54	496.89
	$a_{c,1}=0.90$	$r_{a_{c,1}}=1.11$	-268.21	109.87	158.34
fault-free	$a_{c,1}=1.00$	$r_{a_{c,1}}=1.00$	28.50	-13.55	-14.95
$a_{c,1} > 0$	$a_{c,1}=1.10$	$r_{a_{c,1}}=0.90$	228.91	-93.00	-135.91
	$a_{c,1}=1.30$	$r_{a_{c,1}}=0.77$	662.71	-262.75	-399.96
	$a_{c,1}=1.50$	$r_{a_{c,1}}=0.67$	1044.41	-443.53	-600.88

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230 It can be concluded from Table 3 that, whether it is $a_{c,1} < 0$ faults or $a_{c,1} > 0$
 231 faults, with the serious increase of faults, the deviation between the average value of
 232 ΔM_m increases, which corresponds to the equivalent fault factor $a_{c,1}$ in a nonlinear
 233 manner. Similarly, it also has a nonlinear relationship with the equivalent
 234 compensation factor $r_{a_{c,1}}$. The nonlinear relationship of ΔM_m and $r_{a_{c,1}}$ can be
 235 described as the nonlinear discrete system described in (13).

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$$236 \quad \Delta M_m(k+1) = f(\Delta M_m(k), \dots, \Delta M_m(k-n_{p2}), r_{a_c}(k), \dots, r_{a_c}(k-n_{q2})) \quad (13)$$

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where n_{p2} and n_{q2} coefficients. $\Delta M_m(k) = [\Delta M_{m,1}(k), \Delta M_{m,2}(k), \Delta M_{m,3}(k)]^T$ is the output

238 data at time k , and $r_{a_c}(k) = [r_{a_{c1}}(k) \ r_{a_{c2}}(k) \ r_{a_{c3}}(k)]^T$ is the input data at time k .

239 In this paper, the above nonlinear discrete system is used to design an adaptive
 240 compensator for blade root sensor faults. The dynamic compensation process is
 241 transformed into a real-time control problem of a nonlinear system. The model-free
 242 adaptive control algorithm is used to solve the equivalent compensation factor for
 243 real-time compensation of blade root sensor fault, so as to achieve fault-tolerant
 244 control. The blade root sensor adaptive compensator is similar to the individual pitch
 245 controller. When the system is controllable and observable, the partial derivative of
 246 the control input signal exists, and the system is continuous and satisfies the
 247 generalized Lipschitz assumption, considering the control input criterion function
 248 represented by (14) and the estimation criterion function of the pseudo derivative
 249 represented by (15), (16), (17) And (18).

$$250 \quad J(r_{a_c}(k)) = \|\Delta M_m^*(k+1) - \Delta M_m(k+1)\|^2 + \lambda_c \|r_a(k) - r_a(k-1)\|^2 \quad (14)$$

$$251 \quad J(\Phi_c(k)) = \|\Delta M_m(k) - \Delta M_m(k-1) - \Phi_c(k) \cdot \Delta r_{a_c}(k-1)\|^2 + \mu_c \|\Phi_c(k) -$$

$$252 \quad \hat{\Phi}_c(k-1)\|^2 \quad (15)$$

$$253 \quad \hat{\Phi}_c(k) = \hat{\Phi}_c(k-1) + \frac{\eta_c \Delta r_{a_c}(k-1)}{\mu_c + \|\Delta r_{a_c}(k-1)\|^2} \cdot (\Delta M_m(k) - \Delta M_m(k-1) - \hat{\Phi}_c(k-1) \Delta r_{a_c}(k-1)) \quad (16)$$

$$255 \quad \hat{\Phi}_c(k) = \hat{\Phi}_c(1), \text{ if } |\hat{\Phi}_c(k)| < \varepsilon, \text{ or } |\Delta r_{a_c}(k-1)| < \varepsilon \quad (17)$$

$$256 \quad r_{a_c}(k) = r_{a_c}(k-1) + \frac{\rho_c \hat{\Phi}_c(k)}{\lambda_c + \|\hat{\Phi}_c(k)\|^2} (\Delta M_m^*(k+1) - \Delta M_m(k)) \quad (18)$$

257 where λ_c is a positive weighting factor, $\Delta M_m^*(k+1)$ is the reference output at
 258 $k+1$, μ_c is a positive weighting factor, and $\hat{\Phi}_c(k-1)$ is an estimate of the
 259 pseudo derivative at $k-1$; η_c and ρ_c denote the sequence of steps, respectively,
 260 and ε is a sufficiently small positive number.

261 3.3 Model-free adaptive fault-tolerant individual pitch control

262 Based on the individual pitch controller and fault adaptive compensator proposed
 263 in Sections 3.1 and 3.2, the model-free adaptive fault-tolerant individual pitch control
 264 strategy proposed in this paper is shown in Figure 4. The collective pitch controller is
 265 also designed based on model-free adaptive control. It can be seen from Figure 4 that
 266 the proposed model-free adaptive fault-tolerant control strategy does not require fault
 267 diagnosis and isolation, and does not rely on the model of any controlled object. It
 268 avoids the adverse effects caused by excessive calculation load and modeling error.
 269 The adaptive fault compensator dynamically compensates sensor faults to achieve
 270 fault-tolerant control.

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Figure 4 Model-free adaptive fault-tolerant individual pitch control structure

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4. Simulation results and discussion

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4.1 Simulation environment settings

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The fault-tolerant control strategy proposed in this paper is extensively tested in the joint environment of Matlab/Simulink and FAST. The wind and wave are respectively set as turbulent wind and white noise sound wave, as shown in Figure 5. The parameter settings of CPC, IPC and adaptive compensator are shown in Table 4.

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Figure 5 The turbulent wind and white noise acoustic wave

Table 4 Parameters of the controllers and compensator

Parameters	CPC	IPC	Adaptive compensator for
			sensors
λ	1×10^4	1×10^2	9×10^2
ρ	8×10^{-2}	1.8×10^{-2}	2×10^{-3}
η	1	1	1

μ	10	1×10^{-2}	1×10^{-2}
ε	1×10^{-5}	1×10^{-5}	1×10^{-5}
$\Phi(1)$	-35	[19 0.01; -0.1 -28]	[1 0 0; 0 1 0; 0 0 1]
$\mu(1)$	3	[0 0] ^T	[1 1 1] ^T
$y(1)$	0	[0 0] ^T	[0 0 0] ^T

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284 4.2 Fault-free scenario

285 In this subsection, the model-free adaptive fault-tolerant IPC strategy (MFAC
286 FTIPC) is tested in a fault-free scenario with gain-scheduling PI CPC (GS-PI CPC),
287 gain-scheduling PI IPC (GS-PI IPC), and model-free adaptive IPC (MFAC IPC) as
288 the comparison strategies, and the comparison results are shown in Figure 6.

289 As can be seen in Figure 6(a), the MFAC FTIPC and MFAC IPC have almost the
290 same power generation performance. The power generation of GS-PI IPC, MFAC IPC
291 and MFAC FTIPC with individual pitch is more stable than that of GS-PI CPC with
292 collective pitch, which is due to the fact that GS-PI CPC slows down the pitch
293 amplitude considering that the fast pitch operation will affect the motion of the
294 floating platform, resulting in the fluctuation of power generation. Compared with
295 GS-PI IPC, MFAC IPC and MFAC FTIPC adopt multiple input and multiple output
296 control method, which better solve the coupling problem between yaw and tilt
297 command, so the output power is more stable.

298 From Figure 6(b), it can be seen that the load on the blade roots under MFAC
299 FTIPC and MFAC IPC are also close to each other, and their fluctuation range is
300 significantly smaller than that of GS-PI CPC and GS-PI IPC, indicating that the load
301 on the blade roots can be reduced more effectively by MFAC. It can be seen from
302 Figure 6(c) that the GS-PI CPC is the most effective in controlling the pitching
303 motion of the platform, and the MFAC IPC shows obvious advantages compared with
304 the GS-PI IPC. And MFAC FTIPC has another slight advantage over MFAC IPC,
305 which is due to the dynamic compensation by the compensator, which makes the load
306 on the blade root more balanced and the wheel aerodynamic characteristics more
307 stable, so the floating platform motion is also more stable. Figure 6(d) shows the
308 dynamic compensation process in MFAC FTIPC, and it can be seen that the dynamic
309 compensation factor is kept around 1, i.e., the control effect is close to that of MFAC
310 IPC in the absence of sensor failure.

311 From the above results, MFAC shows obvious advantages over GS-PI, both for
312 power control and load control. In the fault-free scenario, the designed fault
313 compensator for sensors does not interfere with the normal control strategy, on the
314 contrary, under the fault compensator, the blade root is subjected to a more balanced
315 load, which can effectively improve the stability of the FOWT.

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Figure 6 Performance of MFAC FTIPC and the comparison strategies in fault-free scenario

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4.3 Failure scenarios

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4.3.1 Case 1: Fixed bias fault

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In this subsection, the fixed bias fault of blade root moment sensor 2 is simulated and the simulation results are shown in Figure 7. Figures 7(a) and 7(b) show the actual and the measured load on the blade root under MFAC IPC control. It can be seen that after the fault of sensor 2 at 30s, its output increases by a fixed bias of 2000 kN.m. The feedback to the individual pitch controller leads to a large individual pitch component 2 and a large pitch operation of the pitch actuator 2, so the actual blade root of blade 2 is smaller, and the output of the fault sensor is negatively correlated with the actual load on the blade root. The unbalanced moment of the three blades will affect the life of the FOWT in long-term operation under this fault.

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Figures 7(c), 7(d), 7(e) and 7(f) show the actual load on the blade root, the measured load on the blade root, the measured load after compensator compensation and the equivalent compensation factor under MFAC FTIPC, respectively. It can be seen that with the equivalent compensation factor, the fixed bias fault occurred in sensor 2 is quickly compensated, and the load value of blade roots obtained after compensator compensation after 15s is almost the same as the real load applied to the blade root, which means that the adverse effects caused by the fault almost completely disappear and achieve a similar performance as fault-free occurred, which indicates that the proposed MFAC FTIPC does not require fault diagnosis and isolation, and can quickly compensate for sensor fixed deviation faults.

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Figure 7 Performance of MFAC FTIPC and MFAC IPC in Case 1

345 **4.3.2 Case 2: Drift bias fault**

346 To evaluate the performance of the proposed scheme for sensor drift bias fault,
 347 time-varying bias is added to sensor 3 and the simulation results are shown in Figure
 348 8. As can be seen in Figures 8(a) and 8(b), similar to Case 1, the faulty sensor output
 349 is negatively correlated with the actual load applied to the blade root. From 30s
 350 onward, the bias of sensor 3 output becomes larger and larger, and the unbalanced
 351 load on the three blades becomes more and more obvious due to the limited
 352 robustness of MFAC IPC.

353 As can be seen from Figures 8(c), 8(d), 8(e) and 8(f), as the bias of sensor 3
 354 output becomes larger and larger after the fault occurs, the equivalent compensation
 355 factor dynamically compensates in time, which can make the output of the
 356 compensated sensor always close to the actual load borne by the blade root and ensure
 357 that the three blades are subject to balanced load, verifying the effective fault
 358 tolerance of the strategy for sensor offset deviation faults.

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Figure 8 Performance of MFAC FTIPC and MFAC IPC in Case 2

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364 4.3.3 Case 3: Complete failure fault

365 In order to evaluate the performance of the proposed scheme under extreme
 366 sensor fault, the simulation is performed in this subsection for the complete failure
 367 fault of the blade root moment sensor 1. The simulation results are shown in Figure 9.
 368 From Figure 9(a) and 9(b), it can be seen that after the complete failure fault of sensor
 369 1 at 30s, its output is fixed at 4000 kN.m. The feedback to the individual pitch
 370 controller leads to a small pitch operation of the pitch actuator 1, and the bearing
 371 moment of the three blades becomes seriously unbalanced, and the long-term
 372 operation under this failure will seriously affect the life of the FOWT.

373 As can be seen from Figures 9(c), 9(d), 9(e), and 9(f), the complete failure fault
 374 occurring in sensor 1 is quickly compensated by the equivalent compensation factor,
 375 and the adverse effects caused by this fault almost completely disappear, achieving a
 376 similar performance as if no fault occurred, which indicates that the proposed MFAC
 377 FTIPC can quickly compensate for the complete failure fault of the sensor.

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Figure 9 Performance of MFAC FTIPC and MFAC IPC in Case 3

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383 4.3.4 Case 4: Multiple faults co-exist

384 To further evaluate the performance of the proposed scheme under multiple
 385 sensor failures, simulations are performed in this subsection for the simultaneous
 386 complete failure, fixed bias and fixed bias failures of blade root moment sensors 1, 2
 387 and 3, respectively, and the simulation results are shown in Figure 10. From Figure
 388 10(a) and 10(b), it can be seen that after the simultaneous occurrence of three types of
 389 failures on the sensors, a serious imbalance in the bearing moments of the three blades
 390 occurs, which will seriously affect the aerodynamic loads of the FOWT.

391 As shown in Figures 10(c), 10(d), 10(e), and 10(f), all faults are quickly
 392 compensated by the sensor fault compensator, the adverse effects caused by these
 393 faults almost disappear, and all three blade root moments return to normal values,
 394 which indicates that the proposed MFAC FTIPC can cope with multiple sensor faults
 395 occurring simultaneously and has excellent fault-tolerant control capability.

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Figure 10 Performance of MFAC FTIPC and MFAC IPC in Case 4

400 **4.4 Analysis of the generator power, platform motion and structural response of**
 401 **the FOWT**

402 The above simulation results demonstrate the dynamic performance of the
 403 MFAC FTIPC proposed in this paper under the failure of the blade root sensors. In
 404 order to further analyze the effectiveness of the proposed control scheme, the main
 405 control objectives of IPC for the FOWT, namely constant power control, floating
 406 platform stability control and load shedding control, are analyzed in this section.

407 For the power control performance of this scheme, the standard deviation (STD)
 408 and the mean (Mean) of the generator power were calculated to quantify the power
 409 fluctuation and deviation from the rated power, respectively. The calculation results
 410 are shown in Figures 11(a) and 11(b), the fluctuation of the generator power increases
 411 as the severity of the fault increases. The power fluctuation and deviation under
 412 MFAC FTIPC in all fault cases are decreased and close to the performance in the
 413 fault-free scenario, indicating that MFAC FTIPC has significantly improved the
 414 power control and almost completely eliminated the effects caused by the faults.

415 For the floating platform stability control performance of this scheme, due to the

416 limited space, only the STD and Mean of the FOWT aerodynamic load that plays the
 417 main influence on the longitudinal pitching motion are shown in Figures 11(c) and
 418 11(d) (Zhou et al., 2019), it can be seen that in the fault-free scenario, the three blade
 419 root loads are more balanced under MFAC FTIPC due to the compensator and the
 420 wheel is subjected to a more stable load, resulting in a reduced pitch motion of the
 421 platform. The fluctuations and mean values of the floating platform pitch motion
 422 under MFAC FTIPC in all fault cases are significantly reduced and close to the level
 423 in the fault-free scenario, indicating that the MFAC FTIPC makes the pitch motion
 424 tend to the fault-free condition and the aerodynamic load on the wheel is more
 425 balanced by the compensation of the blade root moment sensor under the fault
 426 condition, which makes the floating platform motion more stable.

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429 Figure 11 Analysis of the generator power and the pitch angle of the platform

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431 For the load reduction control performance of this scheme, the STD and Mean of
 432 side-to-side, fore-aft and torsional moments of the tower base are calculated, and the
 433 results are shown in Figure 12, the fluctuation and mean values of the tower base
 434 withstanding moment under MFAC FTIPC proposed in almost all cases are decreased,
 435 especially the fluctuation of the torsional moment, which indicates that MFAC FTIPC
 436 obviously improves the wheel pneumatic load imbalance under various faults, leading
 437 to a more stable tower base withstanding torsional moment and avoiding the tower
 438 base life to be adversely affected under the action of strong alternating torsional
 439 moment.

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Figure 12 Analysis of tower base moments for floating turbines

444 5. Conclusion

445 For the FOWT with multiple faults of the blade root moment sensor, this paper
446 proposes a model-free adaptive fault-tolerant individual pitch control scheme, in
447 which the individual pitch controller and the fault adaptive compensator all adopt
448 model-free adaptive control strategy, which does not require any mathematical
449 modeling of FOWT to avoid modeling tedium and unavoidable errors in modeling,
450 and also does not rely on any fault diagnosis and isolation, and transforms the fault
451 dynamic compensation process into a nonlinear system real-time control problem.
452 The proposed fault-tolerant control strategy is extensively simulated and tested using
453 FAST under fixed bias fault, drift bias fault, complete failure fault and coexistence of
454 multiple fault of the blade root moment sensor, respectively. The simulation results
455 show that the proposed fault-tolerant control strategy not only keeps the bearing load
456 of the wheel balanced, but also reduces the floating platform motion and significantly
457 reduces the bearing load of the FOWT. In addition, the output power is also closer to
458 the rated power, which verifies the excellent fault-tolerance capability of the strategy.
459

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